

STANDARDISATION ON CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A critical phase in the life-cycle of a material is the transition from the development stage to that of design and industrial application. Advanced technical ceramics are currently in this phase and their future market penetration and acceptance as engineering materials critically depend on the availability of a robust set of standards for test methods which allow one to determine their mechanical and thermal properties in a reliable and reproducible way.

In Europe, standardisation on continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CFCCs) officially started in 1989, when CEN TC 184 on Advanced Technical Ceramics was launched. The scope of TC 184 covers testing methods, and no efforts are paid to the development of material and product standards as yet. The work programme of TC 184 in the area of CFCCs, aimed at the establishment of testing methods for the generation of reliable data for design purposes, is reviewed.

The operating mode of the CEN subcommittee responsible for CFCC test standards and the way in which the standard developers interact with pre- and co-normative research in the European Union is described. Links to similar activities in other standardisation organisations such as ASTM, JIS, ISO are indicated. Examples of recent standard developments are given in the subsequent presentations.